

Acceptance of Health Information Application in Smart National Identity Card (SNIC) Using a New I-P Framework

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Abstract : This study discovers a novel framework of individual level technology adoption known as I-P (Individual- Privacy) towards Smart National Identity Card health information application. Many countries introduced smart national identity card (SNIC) with various applications such as health information application embedded inside it. However, the degree to which citizens accept and use some of the embedded applications in smart national identity remains unknown to many governments and application providers as well. Moreover, the previous studies revealed that the factors of trust, perceived risk, privacy concern and perceived credibility need to be incorporated into more comprehensive models such as extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology known as UTAUT2. UTAUT2 is a mainly widespread and leading theory existing in the information system literature up to now. This research identifies factors affecting the citizens' behavioural intention to use health information application embedded in SNIC and extends better understanding on the relevant factors that the government and the application providers would need to consider in predicting citizens' new technology acceptance in the future. We propose a conceptual framework by combining the UTAUT2 and Privacy Calculus Model constructs and also adding perceived credibility as a new variable. The proposed framework may provide assistance to any government planning, decision, and policy makers involving e-government projects. The empirical study may be conducted in the future to provide proof and empirically validate this I-P framework.

Keywords : unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) model, UTAUT2 model, smart national identity card (SNIC), health information application, privacy calculus model (PCM)

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